

COMPARATIVE TYPOLOGY OF THE PLURAL FORM OF NOUNS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Abstract: The purpose of this article is to assert the syntactic and semantic characteristics of comparison in English and Uzbek. Comparative Typology, which dealt with comparing language units and languages that did not have a common root language, was crucial in the emergence and development of this field. The development of Comparative Typology was further aided by the comparison of minor structural languages.

Key words: Typology, comparison, structural languages, language, societal conceptions, characteristics.

The power of words in any language to communicate distinct thoughts existent in this culture, thereby changing their shapes, distinguishes them. The majority of societal conceptions share common characteristics, i.e. they have universal nature.

Among the linguistic categories that may be traced in the majority of the world's languages are those that have a typologically generic nature yet can be articulated differently in various languages. Understanding these linguistic facts and determining their parallels and variances is critical for the man of letters, particularly for graduates of university language faculties who will be English teachers and translators in the near future.

Linguistic concepts such as case, gender, person, tense voice, possession, and so on are of universal character for the comparative languages, but they may be conveyed by typologically diverse ways of the language. In this chapter, we attempt to generalise the key techniques of expressing thoughts that are unique to the comparing languages.

Typological category of case.

Case is a grammatical form that participates in the construction of the paradigm of nouns; in other words, case is a grammatical form that participates in the formation of the paradigm of nouns (or pronouns). Grammarians appear to be divided on the case system used for English nouns. The most widely held belief is that they only have two cases: common (subject) and possessive (genitive). The common case is distinguished by a zero morpheme (suffix) (for example, kid, boy, student, girl), but the possessive case is distinguished by the inflexion '-s and its phonetic variations [s], and [iz].

The English common case and the other five Uzbek instances are identified as members of the case opposition in both languages. The English possessive case is distinguished by the suffix '-s', which can occasionally be replaced by the preposition 'of' (e.g., my father's room > my father's room) and is thus often referred to as the 'of-genitive' case. This case signifies possession of an item or a person, and it has an Uzbek equivalent (*qaratqich kelishigi*), which is denoted by the case ending suffix *-ning*.

Gender Typological Category

The ideas of natural (biological sex) and grammatical (formal) gender comprise the typological category of gender. This category is linked to natural sex since it (this category) defines the gender (sex) of humans, animals, and birds. In English, it is represented through nouns and pronouns. (But, in Russian, it may also be conveyed using adjectives and verbs in the past simple tense.) Most Uzbek grammar texts do not include information regarding the gender category of Uzbek nouns since the writers believe Uzbek nouns do not have this category at all.

Yet, in English, several nouns can be classified as either men or females. Friends, cousins, doctors, neighbours, workers, and so on. The same may be stated of Uzbek kinship terminology. They are said to be of the same (neutral) gender. When no gender distinction is required, the masculine pronoun is used for these nouns.

Gender is expressed in three ways in the compared languages: morphologically, syntactically, and lexically. The morphological approach of indicating the gender category is done by adding gender suffixes to the word.

Typological category of plurality

The category of plurality refers to the system of grammatical expressions that reflect grammatical degree (number). This is the category. Formants representing this category are typically added to the stem of nouns when comparing languages (or pronouns). We must distinguish between logical and grammatical numbers. Proper nouns, from a logical standpoint, generally refer to a particular item or person. For example: John, London, and so on. Common nouns are used to represent common types of objects, which might logically include more than one.

Nouns in plenty.

Uzbek nouns and pronouns commonly signify this number with the suffix *-lar*, which can also be used to show respect for the person being spoken about.

Dadamlar keldilar, for example. (But, keep in mind that you can only have one father).

The following English nouns can express the concept of plurality:

a) by the use of suffixes:

-s, -es (wife-wives, head-heads) (wife-wives, head-heads),

-en (oxen, children, brothers and sisters);

-a datum-data, sanatorium-sanatoria, phenomenon-phenomenon), and so on.

b) by substituting a different root vowel (man-men, goose-geese)

Typological category of person

The category of person should be addressed in tandem with the category of number (plurality). Since in the languages of Indo-European family all categories are conveyed by one and the same morpheme concurrently, i.e. a morpheme expressing number at the same time represents person as well. In Roman, for example, the morpheme -nt indicates both the third person and the plural number in forms such as amant, habent, legunt, amabant, habebunt, and so on.

The category of person is a distinguishing property of pronouns and verbs in comparing languages. They (languages) distinguish three kinds of personal pronouns, designating the person(s) speaking (first person), the person(s) addressed to (second person), and the person(s) (or objects) spoken about (third person).

Aspect is a type of verb that indicates whether the activity described is a continual action or one that occurs always, frequently, or only once. In other words, it is a form of the verb that expresses how the action is carried out, i.e. whether it is a single completed action (or point), a recurring action, or a continuous process. Aspect may also be defined as a verbal form that expresses habituality, continuation, or completeness of the action or situation conveyed by the root of the verb. Aspect is rarely treated as a separate category of the verb in Uzbek grammars since it is not often articulated as clearly as it appears due to the lack of analytical forms.

The notions of tense and aspect are so intertwined in the comparative languages that they cannot be treated individually. Because one and the same form of the verb expresses tense and aspect at the same time, they should be considered 'tense-aspect forms' of the verb.

We differentiate three features of verb forms when comparing languages: simple (common or indefinite), continuous, and perfect. When all of the tense

forms of the verb are combined, they constitute the so-called "tense aspect forms of the verb."

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